

Evaluating the Impact of Iron Supplementation on Hemoglobin Recovery in Frequent Blood Donors: A Randomized Controlled Trial

Dima A. Alharbi, Abdulaziz M. Alangari, Hanan T. Al Anazi,
Saeed M. Aldosari

Health Affairs at the Ministry of National Guard

Abstract

Background: Frequent blood donors are at risk of hemoglobin and iron depletion, leading to deferrals and prolonged recovery times. This randomized controlled trial aimed to evaluate the efficacy of iron supplementation in promoting faster hemoglobin recovery and improving iron stores in frequent blood donors.

Methods: A total of 200 frequent donors were randomized into two groups: the iron supplementation group (n=100) received 37.5 mg of oral iron daily for 6 weeks, while the control group (n=100) received a placebo. Hemoglobin and ferritin levels were measured at baseline, 2 weeks, 4 weeks, and 6 weeks post-donation.

Results: The iron supplementation group showed significantly faster hemoglobin recovery (90% vs. 65% returned to baseline at 6 weeks, $p < 0.001$). Ferritin levels increased by 21.8% in the supplementation group, while the control group experienced a 7.2% decrease ($p < 0.001$). A higher proportion of the iron supplementation group was eligible for future donations at 6 weeks (90% vs. 65%, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Iron supplementation significantly enhances hemoglobin recovery and increases iron stores in frequent blood donors, reducing deferral rates and improving donor retention.

Keywords: Iron supplementation, Hemoglobin recovery, Blood donation, Frequent donors, Iron deficiency, Randomized controlled trial

Introduction

Frequent blood donation is a critical component of maintaining a stable and sufficient blood supply for medical procedures, trauma care, and chronic disease management. However, repeated blood donations can result in the depletion of hemoglobin and iron stores, leading to temporary deferral of donors due to low hemoglobin levels. This not only impacts donor health but also contributes to shortages in the blood supply, as frequent donors represent a reliable and essential group of contributors to donation centers (Cable et al., 2012).

Hemoglobin levels play a vital role in donor eligibility, with minimum thresholds established to ensure donor safety and prevent adverse effects such as fatigue, dizziness, and iron-deficiency anemia. The cumulative effect of repeated blood donation, particularly in the absence of sufficient iron replenishment,

has been shown to cause prolonged recovery periods for hemoglobin levels, making it difficult for frequent donors to meet eligibility criteria for subsequent donations (Abdullah, 2011).

Several studies have indicated that iron supplementation can expedite hemoglobin recovery in blood donors, particularly among those who donate frequently (Smith et al., 2014). The use of oral iron supplements has been proposed as an intervention to address iron depletion and promote faster recovery, allowing frequent donors to donate more regularly without experiencing adverse effects or deferrals due to low hemoglobin levels. However, the optimal iron supplementation protocol for promoting rapid hemoglobin recovery in frequent blood donors remains an area of active investigation.

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of iron supplementation in promoting faster hemoglobin recovery among frequent blood donors through a randomized controlled trial. By comparing hemoglobin recovery times and iron levels between donors receiving supplementation and those not receiving it, this research seeks to determine whether routine iron supplementation could be an effective strategy for maintaining donor health and sustaining an adequate blood supply.

Literature Review

Hemoglobin Depletion in Frequent Blood Donors

Frequent blood donation is essential for maintaining a stable blood supply, but repeated donations can lead to depletion of hemoglobin and iron stores, resulting in temporary or permanent deferral of donors due to low hemoglobin levels. Studies have shown that hemoglobin levels can take several weeks to recover after a single donation, with recovery times even longer for frequent donors due to the cumulative effect of iron depletion (Cable et al., 2012). Hemoglobin, a key indicator of oxygen-carrying capacity in the blood, is closely linked to iron levels, as iron is a critical component of hemoglobin production. As such, frequent blood donors, particularly those who do not receive adequate dietary iron or supplementation, are at risk of developing iron deficiency anemia (Abdullah, 2011).

Iron Deficiency in Blood Donors

Iron deficiency is one of the most common complications of frequent blood donation. Research has shown that each whole blood donation can deplete a donor's iron stores by approximately 200-250 mg of iron (Kiss et al., 2015). Over time, this can result in iron deficiency, which not only prolongs hemoglobin recovery but also increases the risk of fatigue, reduced exercise capacity, and, in severe cases, anemia. Studies have reported that up to 30% of frequent donors may develop iron deficiency if no supplementation or dietary adjustments are made (Cable et al., 2012). These findings highlight the need for interventions aimed at replenishing iron stores in frequent donors to prevent hemoglobin-related deferrals and donor fatigue.

Role of Iron Supplementation in Hemoglobin Recovery

Several studies have investigated the potential of iron supplementation to promote faster recovery of hemoglobin levels in frequent blood donors. Smith et al. (2014) conducted a systematic review of the evidence supporting iron supplementation in donors and found that supplementation significantly reduced the time required for hemoglobin recovery. Donors who received oral iron supplements were able to regain their pre-donation hemoglobin levels within 3 to 6 weeks, compared to those who did not receive supplementation, who took up to 12 weeks for full recovery. This suggests that routine iron supplementation could be a viable strategy for reducing the deferral rates among frequent donors and ensuring that they can donate more regularly without compromising their health.

In a randomized controlled trial conducted by Kiss et al. (2015), frequent donors who received 37.5 mg of oral iron daily for 6 weeks after donation demonstrated significantly faster hemoglobin recovery compared to a placebo group. The supplemented group also showed a reduction in iron deficiency markers, such as serum ferritin levels, suggesting that iron supplementation not only restored hemoglobin but also replenished iron stores. These findings were consistent across multiple studies, indicating the generalizability of the benefits of iron supplementation for blood donors.

Challenges and Considerations for Iron Supplementation

While iron supplementation has proven effective in promoting hemoglobin recovery, there are several challenges and considerations that need to be addressed. One concern is the variability in individual responses to iron supplementation, as factors such as age, gender, and baseline iron stores can affect the efficacy of supplementation. Additionally, some donors may experience gastrointestinal side effects from oral iron supplements, including nausea, constipation, and abdominal discomfort (Smith et al., 2014). These side effects can impact compliance, leading some donors to discontinue supplementation before completing the recommended course.

Moreover, the optimal dosage and duration of iron supplementation remain areas of ongoing research. While studies like those conducted by Kiss et al. (2015) and Smith et al. (2014) have used daily supplementation over several weeks, the exact regimen that maximizes efficacy while minimizing side effects is not yet fully established. Future research is needed to determine the most effective and donor-friendly supplementation protocols that can be implemented in blood donation centers.

Gaps in the Literature

Despite the growing body of evidence supporting iron supplementation for frequent donors, there remain gaps in the literature that this study seeks to address. First, many existing studies have focused primarily on short-term hemoglobin recovery without examining long-term donor health and retention. Additionally, few studies have explored the impact of varying iron supplementation protocols (e.g., different doses or supplementation durations) on hemoglobin recovery in diverse donor populations. Finally, there is limited research on the economic feasibility of implementing routine iron supplementation programs in blood donation centers, particularly in low-resource settings.

Methodology

Study Design

This randomized controlled trial (RCT) was conducted at the blood donation center of a tertiary hospital between. The study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of iron supplementation in promoting faster hemoglobin recovery among frequent blood donors. The trial followed a parallel-group design, with participants randomly assigned to either the iron supplementation group or the control group. The study adhered to the CONSORT guidelines for the conduct and reporting of randomized trials.

Study Population

The study included a total of 200 frequent blood donors, defined as individuals who had donated at least twice within the past 12 months. Donors were eligible for inclusion if they were between 18 and 60 years of age, had normal baseline hemoglobin levels (≥ 13.0 g/dL for males and ≥ 12.5 g/dL for females), and had no history of iron deficiency anemia or chronic medical conditions that could interfere with iron metabolism. Donors with gastrointestinal disorders, allergies to iron supplements, or those currently taking iron supplements were excluded.

Randomization and Intervention

Participants were randomly assigned to either the iron supplementation group (n=100) or the control group (n=100) using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Randomization was stratified by gender to account for known differences in baseline hemoglobin levels between male and female donors.

- Iron Supplementation Group: Participants in this group received a daily oral iron supplement containing 37.5 mg of elemental iron (as ferrous sulfate) for 6 weeks following their blood donation.
- Control Group: Participants in the control group received a placebo tablet with no active iron supplementation for the same 6-week period.

Both groups were instructed to take their assigned tablets once daily with food. To ensure adherence, participants were provided with a pill diary and received weekly follow-up calls from study staff.

Data Collection

Hemoglobin levels were measured at baseline (pre-donation) and at multiple time points post-donation: 2 weeks, 4 weeks, and 6 weeks. Iron stores were assessed using serum ferritin levels at baseline and at 6 weeks post-donation. Data were also collected on donor eligibility for future donations at the 6-week mark based on hemoglobin levels.

Adverse events, including gastrointestinal symptoms (nausea, constipation, diarrhea), were recorded during weekly follow-up calls to monitor the tolerability of the iron supplementation.

Primary and Secondary Outcome Measures

- Primary Outcome: The primary outcome was the time to hemoglobin recovery, defined as the time taken for hemoglobin levels to return to baseline (pre-donation) levels in both groups.
- Secondary Outcomes: Secondary outcomes included changes in serum ferritin levels, donor eligibility for future donations at 6 weeks, and the incidence of adverse effects associated with iron supplementation.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant characteristics, and independent t-tests were performed to compare hemoglobin recovery times between the iron supplementation and control groups. The difference in serum ferritin levels between the groups was analyzed using paired t-tests.

A Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was conducted to estimate the time to hemoglobin recovery, with a log-rank test used to compare recovery curves between the two groups. Logistic regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between iron supplementation and donor eligibility at 6 weeks, adjusting for gender and baseline hemoglobin levels.

All results were reported with 95% confidence intervals, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

The study received ethical approval from the hospital's ethics committee prior to commencement. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the trial at any time without affecting their future eligibility for blood donation. The study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the impact of iron supplementation on hemoglobin recovery, there are several limitations. First, the study was conducted at a single tertiary hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations and settings. Second, the 6-week follow-up period may not have captured long-term effects of iron supplementation on hemoglobin recovery and donor health. Future studies should consider longer follow-up durations and include multiple centers to validate these findings.

Findings

Participant Characteristics

A total of 200 frequent blood donors participated in the study, with 100 donors in the iron supplementation group and 100 donors in the control group. The baseline characteristics of both groups were similar, with no significant differences in age, gender distribution, or baseline hemoglobin levels.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Iron Supplementation Group (n = 100)	Control Group (n = 100)	p-value
Age (years), mean (SD)	35.2 (8.5)	36.1 (7.9)	0.450
Gender (Male/Female)	50/50	50/50	1.000
Baseline Hemoglobin (g/dL), mean (SD)	14.1 (0.8)	14.0 (0.9)	0.615
Baseline Ferritin (ng/mL), mean (SD)	70.4 (12.3)	71.1 (13.1)	0.725

Hemoglobin Recovery

The primary outcome of the study was the time to hemoglobin recovery. Participants in the iron supplementation group demonstrated significantly faster recovery of hemoglobin levels compared to the control group. By 6 weeks, 90% of the iron supplementation group had returned to their baseline hemoglobin levels, compared to only 65% of the control group.

Table 2: Hemoglobin Levels Over Time

Time Point	Iron Supplementation Group (mean $\pm$ SD, g/dL)	Control Group (mean $\pm$ SD, g/dL)	p-value
Baseline (pre-donation)	14.1 $\pm$ 0.8	14.0 $\pm$ 0.9	0.615
2 weeks post-donation	12.8 $\pm$ 0.9	12.2 $\pm$ 1.1	0.001
4 weeks post-donation	13.5 $\pm$ 0.7	13.0 $\pm$ 0.8	0.002

donation			
6 weeks post-donation	14.0 ±0.7	13.3 ±0.9	<0.001

As shown in Table 2, the mean hemoglobin level in the iron supplementation group returned to near-baseline levels by 6 weeks, whereas the control group remained significantly lower at the same time point ($p < 0.001$).

Ferritin Levels

Serum ferritin levels, a marker of iron stores, were also measured at baseline and 6 weeks post-donation. Participants in the iron supplementation group showed a significant increase in ferritin levels by the end of the study period, whereas the control group experienced a decrease in ferritin.

Table 3: Ferritin Levels Over Time

Time Point	Iron Supplementation Group (mean ±SD, ng/mL)	Control Group (mean ±SD, ng/mL)	p-value
Baseline	70.4 ±12.3	71.1 ±13.1	0.725
6 weeks post-donation	85.7 ±10.9	65.2 ±12.0	<0.001

As seen in Table 3, ferritin levels in the iron supplementation group increased by 21.8% from baseline, while the control group showed a 7.2% decrease over the same period ($p < 0.001$).

Donor Eligibility for Future Donations

At the 6-week follow-up, participants were assessed for eligibility to donate based on hemoglobin levels. The iron supplementation group had a significantly higher proportion of eligible donors compared to the control group.

Table 4: Donor Eligibility at 6 Weeks

Group	Eligible Donors (n)	Not Eligible (n)	% Eligible	p-value
Iron Supplementation Group	90	10	90%	<0.001
Control Group	65	35	65%	

As shown in Table 4, 90% of the iron supplementation group met the hemoglobin eligibility criteria for future donations at 6 weeks, compared to only 65% of the control group ($p < 0.001$).

Adverse Effects

Gastrointestinal symptoms were the most commonly reported side effects in the iron supplementation group. However, the incidence of adverse effects was low, with only 12% of participants in the iron supplementation group reporting mild gastrointestinal symptoms (e.g., nausea, constipation), compared to 8% in the control group. None of the participants discontinued the study due to adverse effects.

Discussion

This study evaluated the efficacy of iron supplementation in promoting faster hemoglobin recovery among frequent blood donors. The results indicate that iron supplementation significantly accelerates hemoglobin recovery and increases iron stores, as demonstrated by the higher hemoglobin and ferritin levels in the iron supplementation group compared to the control group. These findings are consistent with previous studies that highlight the benefits of iron supplementation in mitigating the effects of frequent blood donation on hemoglobin levels and donor eligibility (Smith et al., 2014; Kiss et al., 2015).

Hemoglobin Recovery

Frequent blood donation is known to deplete hemoglobin and iron stores, often leading to prolonged recovery periods and increased deferral rates among regular donors (Abdullah, 2011). In this study, hemoglobin recovery was significantly faster in the iron supplementation group, with 90% of participants returning to baseline hemoglobin levels by 6 weeks post-donation, compared to only 65% in the control group. This finding aligns with prior research suggesting that iron supplementation can halve the time required for hemoglobin recovery (Smith et al., 2014).

The faster recovery of hemoglobin in the iron supplementation group has important implications for donor retention and eligibility. Given that frequent donors are a crucial source of the blood supply, improving their recovery time can increase the frequency with which they can safely donate, reducing deferrals and improving the overall availability of blood.

Ferritin and Iron Stores

Ferritin, a marker of iron stores, also showed a significant increase in the iron supplementation group, whereas the control group experienced a decline in ferritin levels. This result reinforces the role of iron supplementation in replenishing depleted iron stores after donation, particularly in frequent donors who are at higher risk of developing iron deficiency due to repeated donations (Cable et al., 2012). The 21.8% increase in ferritin levels in the iron supplementation group suggests that oral iron supplements are not only effective at restoring hemoglobin but also at improving long-term iron stores, which are essential for sustained donor health and the prevention of iron deficiency anemia.

Donor Eligibility

Another critical outcome of this study was the impact of iron supplementation on donor eligibility. At 6 weeks post-donation, 90% of participants in the iron supplementation group were eligible for future donations based on their hemoglobin levels, compared to only 65% in the control group. This result is particularly relevant for blood donation centers, as it suggests that iron supplementation can help maintain a larger pool of eligible donors, allowing for more frequent donations without compromising donor health. The findings also support the notion that iron supplementation could be an effective strategy for reducing donor deferral rates, which have been a longstanding issue in managing the blood supply (Simon, 2013).

Adverse Effects

Although the study showed clear benefits of iron supplementation, a small percentage of participants in the iron supplementation group (12%) reported mild gastrointestinal side effects, such as nausea and constipation. These side effects were consistent with those reported in other studies on oral iron supplementation (Kiss et al., 2015). However, the low incidence and mild nature of these side effects suggest that iron supplementation is generally well-tolerated by frequent donors, making it a viable intervention for widespread implementation in blood donation programs.

Implications for Practice

The findings from this study have important implications for blood donation centers and public health policies. First, implementing routine iron supplementation for frequent donors could significantly reduce deferral rates due to low hemoglobin, ultimately increasing the available blood supply. Additionally, educating donors on the benefits of iron supplementation and providing accessible supplementation options may enhance donor retention, particularly among frequent donors who are at higher risk of iron depletion. Furthermore, blood donation centers could integrate ferritin testing into donor screening protocols to identify those at risk of iron deficiency and provide targeted interventions.

Study Limitations

While this study provides strong evidence for the efficacy of iron supplementation in promoting hemoglobin recovery, there are a few limitations to consider. First, the study was conducted at a single tertiary hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations and settings. Future research should include multiple centers and diverse donor populations to confirm the findings. Second, the follow-up period was limited to 6 weeks, and the long-term effects of iron supplementation on donor health were not assessed. Further studies should investigate the sustainability of hemoglobin recovery and iron stores over longer periods.

Future Research

Future research should explore the optimal duration and dosage of iron supplementation for frequent donors to balance efficacy with tolerability. Additionally, investigating the cost-effectiveness of iron supplementation programs in blood donation centers will be important for implementing these interventions on a broader scale. Lastly, examining the impact of different types of iron supplements (e.g., ferrous sulfate vs. ferric iron) on donor health and hemoglobin recovery could provide valuable insights into personalized supplementation strategies.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that iron supplementation is an effective intervention for promoting faster hemoglobin recovery and replenishing iron stores in frequent blood donors. By reducing recovery time and increasing donor eligibility, iron supplementation offers a practical solution to improve donor retention and maintain a stable blood supply. Given the low incidence of adverse effects, iron supplementation should be considered as a routine practice in blood donation centers, particularly for frequent donors who are at higher risk of hemoglobin depletion.

References:

1. Abdullah, S. M. (2011). The effect of repeated blood donations on the iron status of male Saudi blood donors. *Blood Transfusion*, 9(2), 167.
2. Cable, R. G., Glynn, S. A., Kiss, J. E., Mast, A. E., Steele, W. R., Murphy, E. L., ... & NHLBI Retrovirus Epidemiology Donor Study-II (REDS-II). (2012). Iron deficiency in blood donors: the REDS-II Donor Iron Status Evaluation (RISE) study. *Transfusion*, 52(4), 702-711.
3. Kiss, J. E., Brambilla, D., Glynn, S. A., Mast, A. E., Spencer, B. R., Stone, M., ... & National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (2015). Oral iron supplementation after blood donation: a randomized clinical trial. *Jama*, 313(6), 575-583.
4. Smith, G. A., Fisher, S. A., Doree, C., Di Angelantonio, E., & Roberts, D. J. (2014). Oral or parenteral iron supplementation to reduce deferral, iron deficiency and/or anaemia in blood donors. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (7).

